

Metadata description for archival material

Title: Archival material from the pamphlet and historical papers collection at the Library of the Nordic Africa Institute, Nordic Africa Institute, Uppsala

Description: A selection of the pamphlet and other historical papers collection at the Library of the Nordic Africa Institute. The material contains a curated collection of papers on a variety of topics relating to Africa from the late 1940s to 1990, especially as regards to politics, development cooperation, historical papers, African regionalism, and regional cooperation.

Pamphlet and historical papers collection, curated on a box-by-box basis. Data was collected from the following boxes:

Boxes on History: -1965, 1966-1973, 1974-

Boxes on Political Science: -1956, 1957-1967, 1968-1988, 1990-

Boxes on Development Aid: -1963, 1964-1967, 1968-,

Boxes on Development Aid (Sida): -1971,

Boxes on development Aid (Technical Assistance): 1949-1972

Boxes on Regional Cooperation

Boxes on Regional Cooperation (AAPSO)

Boxes on Migration Refugee Policy: -1989

Boxes on UN: 1970-1991

Boxes on IR

Boxes on OBF

Boxes on Socialism: -1979

Boxes on Sociology: -1979

Boxes on Social History: 1975-1983

Boxes on Money and Banking

Boxes on International Capital Movements

The material contains physical photocopies.

Date of data collection: 25.4-24.5.2023

Keywords: Africa, Development, History, Regional Cooperation, Regionalism, Ideology.

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Preservation of research data: The material will be stored in a private capacity.